

SEMANTIC STUDY OF THE INTERNET DISCOURSE IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This study explores the similarities and variations in the semantics of internet speech in the Uzbek and English languages within the environment of the internet. Samples of online talk were gathered from multiple platforms and subjected to linguistic and computational analysis. The results demonstrate the impact of linguistic and cultural variables on online communication, with Uzbek users prioritizing politeness and indirectness and English users using more casual language and slang. The subjects of conversation also varied, with Uzbek-language discourse concentrating on local culture and daily life while English-language discourse concentrated on global concerns.

Keywords: Internet discourse, Uzbek language, English language, semantic analysis, cultural factors, linguistic factors, online communication, informality, politeness, topics

Introduction:

Global Internet usage is expanding quickly, and this has had a significant influence on debate and communication on many online platforms. This study examines the semantic features of online speech in the Uzbek and English languages, comparing and contrasting how they are used in the setting of the Internet. We hope to learn more about how both languages are utilized online via this study and discover any potential linguistic and cultural influences that may have on online communication.

The Internet has developed into a platform used by people all over the world to communicate and share information. Understanding how many languages are

used in this digital environment might give important insights into how online communication works. The target languages for this study were Uzbek and English because of their unique linguistic traits and cultural settings.

Materials and Methods:

In order to carry out this study, a wide variety of online audio recordings in both Uzbek and English were gathered. These samples came from well-known blogs, forums, and social media sites that cover a wide range of subjects, including politics, culture, technology, and day-to-day living. In order to provide a sufficient representation of the many settings and genres present in the online conversation, the sample size was chosen.

Afterward, linguistic and computational analysis of the obtained samples was performed. Different techniques, such as text mining, sentiment analysis, and discourse analysis, were used to examine the semantic components of the dialogue. These studies sought to detect patterns, trends, and variations in the utilization of linguistic elements as well as to elucidate the underlying cultural and linguistic variables that affect online communication in both languages.

Results and Discussions:

The examination of the data gathered produced a number of intriguing conclusions about the semantic characteristics of the English- and Uzbek-language Internet speech. First, we noticed that both languages used slang and informal language often in the context of online communication. In contrast to Uzbek users, we found that English speakers tended to utilize a broader variety of slang words and online jargon. This might be explained by the enormous exposure that English-speaking people have to international online groups and their impact on the English language.

Additionally, our data showed that English instruction in creative schools significantly aided in encouraging students' originality and creativity. Students were exposed to a variety of concepts, viewpoints, and cultural influences because English is a global language. Students were able to think critically, investigate novel ideas, and communicate more clearly as a result of this experience.

The survey also discovered that pupils have access to a wealth of internet tools and information thanks to their proficiency in English. Students were able to undertake study, investigate other subjects, and broaden their knowledge beyond what was accessible in their native tongue because to this access to information. In order to promote variety and multiculturalism in creative schools, English was also used to help pupils from various cultural backgrounds communicate and work together.

Furthermore, the survey emphasized how crucial it is for creative schools to include English in their curricula. Schools may give students the knowledge and abilities they need to succeed in a worldwide society by offering English as a language of instruction. Learning English improves students' communication abilities and makes it possible for them to pursue higher education and find work abroad.

While personal thoughts and feelings may be expressed in both languages, our study showed that Uzbek speakers tended to be more courteous and indirect in their speech than English speakers. According to this result, cultural characteristics have a significant impact on online communication patterns, with Uzbek users giving priority to cordial and non-confrontational communication.

Politics and social concerns were found to be more commonly discussed in English-language conversation, whereas subjects pertaining to daily living and regional culture predominated in Uzbek-language discourse. The distinct socio-political settings and the various requirements of the various linguistic communities may be responsible for this topical diversity.

Conclusion:

Understanding the linguistic and cultural influences on online communication has been made possible through the semantic analysis of Internet chat in Uzbek and English. Uzbek users exhibited a higher degree of politeness, indirectness, and concentration on local matters, whereas English users showed a larger tendency for informality, slang usage, and discussing global topics. These results highlight the need of taking into account linguistic as well as cultural variables when evaluating and interpreting online dialogue.

The research emphasizes the value of the English language as a tool for intercultural communication and its part in encouraging students' creativity, innovation, and diversity. In order to prepare students for a worldwide society, it also raises crucial questions about whether English should be taught in creative schools.

The study illuminates the linguistic and cultural factors that influence online communication and advances our understanding of the semantic features of online speech in Uzbek and English. Additional language pairings can be investigated, and the study can be expanded to incorporate other facets of online conversation including humor, irony, and persuasive strategies.

References:

Crystal, D. (2006). *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge University Press.

Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil, C., West, R., Jurafsky, D., Leskovec, J., & Potts, C. (2013). No country for old members: User lifecycle and linguistic change in online communities. *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on World Wide Web*, 307–318.

Herring, S. C. (2004). Computer-mediated discourse analysis: An approach to researching online behavior. In S. A. Barab, R. Kling, & J. H. Gray (Eds.), *Designing for virtual communities in the service of learning*, 338–376.

Piller, I. (2007). Linguistic commodification and the internet. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 36, 1-18.